

D5.4

Online self-assessment tool

RdA Climate Solutions

The HOOP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101000836.

Document information

Project Title	Hub of circular cities bOO sting P latform to foster investments for the valorisation of urban biowaste and wastewater
Project Acronym	HOOP
Grant Agreement No.	101000836
Project Call	CE-FNR-17-2020
Project Duration	48 months: 1 October 2020 – 30 September 2024
Project URL	https://hooproject.eu/
Work Package	5
Deliverable	D5.4 Online self-assessment tool
Lead Partner	RdA Climate Solutions
Contributing Partner(s)	SAV
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual delivery date	31 st May 2024
Actual delivery date	27 th May 2024
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Document history	Draft 1 sent to WP leaders and Project Coordinator on 30 th April 2024. Final version ready for submission on 27 th May 2024.

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Tool description and weblink

This deliverable D5.4 introduces the online self-assessment tool, which was based on the Project Maturity Level (PML) ranking, available on the HOOP Hub website.

The PML ranking concept is generally accepted as common language and is widely used among European investors, banks, companies, and public agencies.

The HOOP PML self-assessment tool is a **standard guidance, questionnaire and ranking that evaluates the maturity level of the circular bioeconomy projects in accordance with a grade where each level has several criteria to accomplish and reach**, in order to improve the maturity and bankability towards a green financing and funding for the project implementation.

Therefore, the HOOP PML approach is aimed to support project developers, promoters, and investors to evaluate which parts of their project are investment-ready and which criteria need further development and compliance. At the same time, this tool will also contribute for the matchmaking between project developers/promoters and investors, **contributing to assess and improve the maturity and bankability of circular bioeconomy projects**.

This tool, the PML calculator with its criteria and dashboard, was **based on best practice of the financial industry**. It was developed by RdA Climate Solutions based on consultation of investors, contributions from HOOP Circular Investors Board, review from HOOP partners and the public PML Workshop held during the HOOP's Circular Investors Day 2022. The workshop had contributions from investors, banks, enterprises, project developers, cities, public entities, among others. It is also relevant to mention that programmes such as the "Smart Cities Marketplace" of European Commission uses a similar approach for the matchmaking of projects and investors.

The online **PML tool consists of a ranking of 6 maturity levels**, as showed below in Figure 1, with specific criteria for each level, reaching the total of **43 qualitative indicators**.

Figure 1 – Project Maturity Level (PML) ranking.

Hence, the **online tool is composed by 6 sets of criteria to be answered linked to the PML ranking**. Each criterium/indicator should be answered as qualitative, being automatically scored accordingly to the following rationale: “Yes” and “Yes, totally” is scored with 1, “Yes, partially” is scored with 0.5, “No” is scored with 0 and “Not Applicable” means that criterium is removed from the calculation.

All users can self-assess their projects and respective portfolios. Once all criteria have been fulfilled, the tool will automatically produce: a) **a graph with the percentage of compliance** for each PML and, b) **a table with the final score** that ranks the project according with the PMLs described in Figure 1. Each level of the PML will be reached if at least 50% of the level criteria are met. To reach PML 6, at least 75% of PML 5 criteria need to be accomplished and 100% of the lower PML.

By the end, the questionnaire, answers and dashboard with graph and table can be downloaded and/or printed in the form of a report.

The **online PML self-assessment tool is public and available on the HOOP Hub platform**, which can be viewed and used free of charges here: https://hoop-hub.eu/project_maturity_level.html

The tool concept, calculator and script were developed by RdA Climate Solutions and the editing and web developing was done by SAV.

There is a **Guidelines book as supporting the filling of the online PML tool**, developed in deliverable D5.3 “Circular Evaluation Framework Guidance Report”, which is public and available on the HOOP Hub platform: https://hoop-hub.eu/virtual_images/146-96a7e4777036903ff15002dcb7dafa62.pdf